

DroidBot crashes in cleanup when no emulator is up #4

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DroidBot crashed when no emulator was up. The main failure was because ADB could not find emulator-5554. That is a normal external failure mode. However, instead of a clean error message and properly exiting (with a clean exit) it crashed:

```

kevenmen@node0:~/fuzzing_run_1/output/default/crashes$ python3 /users/kevenmen/droidbot/start.py -d emulator
INFO:Device:disable minicap on emulator
adb: device 'emulator-5554' not found
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 87, in __init__
    self.device = Device(
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/device.py", line 100, in __init__
    if self.get_sdk_version() >= 32:
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/device.py", line 227, in get_sdk_version
    self.sdk_version = self.adb.get_sdk_version()
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/adapter/adb.py", line 129, in get_sdk_version
    return int(self.get_property(ADB.VERSION_SDK_PROPERTY))
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/adapter/adb.py", line 117, in get_property
    return self.shell(["getprop", property_name])
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/adapter/adb.py", line 89, in shell
    return self.run_cmd(shell_extra_args)
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/adapter/adb.py", line 68, in run_cmd
    r = subprocess.check_output(args).strip()
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/subprocess.py", line 421, in check_output
    return run(*popenargs, stdout=PIPE, timeout=timeout, check=True,
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/subprocess.py", line 526, in run
    raise CalledProcessError(retcode, process.args,
subprocess.CalledProcessError: Command '['adb', '-s', 'emulator-5554', 'shell', 'getprop', 'ro.build.version.sdk']'
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 87, in __init__
    self.device = Device(
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/device.py", line 100, in __init__
    if self.get_sdk_version() >= 32:
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/device.py", line 227, in get_sdk_version
    self.sdk_version = self.adb.get_sdk_version()
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/adapter/adb.py", line 129, in get_sdk_version
    return int(self.get_property(ADB.VERSION_SDK_PROPERTY))
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    raise CalledProcessError(retcode, process.args,
subprocess.CalledProcessError: Command '['adb', '-s', 'emulator-5554', 'shell', 'getprop', 'ro.build.version.sdk']'

During handling of the above exception, another exception occurred:

Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/start.py", line 196, in <module>
    main()
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/start.py", line 167, in main
    droidbot = DroidBot(
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 116, in __init__
    self.stop()
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 188, in stop
    self.device.tear_down()
AttributeError: 'NoneType' object has no attribute 'tear_down'
kevenmen@node0:~/fuzzing_run_1/output/default/crashes$

```

That is, the error `AttributeError: 'NoneType' object has no attribute 'tear_down'` is a bug because the tool should handle "device init failed" gracefully and exit with a clear error instead of raising a second exception, instead of these messy error traces.

Expected behaviour: handle "device init failed" gracefully and exit without a crash.

Spec:
x86
Python 3.10.12
gcc (Ubuntu 11.4.0-1ubuntu1~22.04.3) 11.4.0

added [crash](#) [droidbot](#) [blackbox fuzzing](#) last week

This is true to all errors, the droidbot just crash, the error is deep in the logs. Like, in the case of this [Failed to parse APK: Bad CRC-32 for AndroidManifest.xml](#):

We get a long trace too:

```

kevenmen@node0:~$ python3 /users/kevenmen/droidbot/start.py -d emulator-5554 -policy bfs_greedy -count 100
INFO:Device:disable minicap on emulator
INFO:Device:disable minicap on sdk >= 32
INFO:androguard.apk:Starting analysis on AndroidManifest.xml
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 96, in __init__
    self.app = App(app_path, output_dir=self.output_dir)
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/app.py", line 29, in __init__
    self.apk = APK(self.app_path)
  File "/users/kevenmen/.local/lib/python3.10/site-packages/androguard/core/bytcodes/apk.py", line 291, in __init__
    self._apk_analysis()
  File "/users/kevenmen/.local/lib/python3.10/site-packages/androguard/core/bytcodes/apk.py", line 311, in _apk_analysis
    manifest_data = self.zip.read(i)
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 1500, in read
    return fp.read()
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 932, in read
    buf += self._read1(self.MAX_N)
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 1036, in _read1
    self._update_crc(data)
  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 964, in _update_crc
    raise BadZipFile("Bad CRC-32 for file %r" % self.name)
zipfile.BadZipFile: Bad CRC-32 for file 'AndroidManifest.xml'
[CONNECTION] ADB is disconnected
WARNING:DroidBotIme:Failed to disconnect DroidBotIME!
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 96, in __init__
    self.app = App(app_path, output_dir=self.output_dir)
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/app.py", line 29, in __init__
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  File "/usr/lib/python3.10/zipfile.py", line 964, in _update_crc
    raise BadZipFile("Bad CRC-32 for file %r" % self.name)
zipfile.BadZipFile: Bad CRC-32 for file 'AndroidManifest.xml'

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    droidbot = DroidBot(
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 116, in __init__
    self.stop()
  File "/users/kevenmen/droidbot/droidbot/droidbot.py", line 191, in stop
    if hasattr(self.input_manager.policy, "master") and \
AttributeError: 'NoneType' object has no attribute 'policy'
kevenmen@node0:~$

```

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[happymod_1774609058_716007651.zip](#)

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